

Clinical profile and management of Posner Schlossman syndromeSuprabha Chandran¹, Rajeev Kumar², Rajeev Kumar Singh³¹Senior Resident, Department of Ophthalmology, Sri Krishna Medical College & Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Sri Krishna Medical College & Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India³Professor & Head, Department of Ophthalmology, Sri Krishna Medical College & Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Objectives:** The present study was to evaluate the clinical profile and management of Posner Schlossman syndrome in tertiary care center of North Bihar.**Methods:** The diagnosis of PSS was made on the basis of the presence of mainly unilateral recurrent mild non-granulomatous iritis with cells in the anterior chamber, with/without fine KPs, elevated IOP, open angles on gonioscopy, without posterior synechiae or posterior uveitis, with the attack lasting few days to weeks. Other causes of uveitis were ruled out by certain investigations: tuberculin skin test, chest X-ray, venereal disease research laboratory test (VDRL), fluorescent treponemal antibody absorption test (FTA-ABS), IgG for toxoplasmosis, and serum angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) test.**Results:** Out of the 30 patients with PSS, 16(53.33%) were affected in the right eye and 9(30%) were affected in the left eye. In 5(16.67%) patients, the affliction was bilateral in nature. Out of 36 eyes, cataract was seen in 3(8.33%) eyes and glaucoma in 10(27.78%) eyes. 22(61.11%) eyes had mild or no visual impairment (visual acuity better than 20/70), 4(11.11%) eyes had moderate visual impairment (<20/70 to 20/200). 1(2.78%) eye had severe visual impairment (<20/200 to 20/400). 2(5.55%) eyes had blindness (>20/400 to 20/1200). 1(2.78%) eye had blindness (>20/1200 to PL). 1(2.78%) eye had blindness (NPL). And the visual acuity was undetermined or unspecified in 5(13.89%) eyes. The mean logMAR at presentation was 0.43 ± 0.65 .**Conclusions:** PSS is more common in young to middle aged population. It is predominantly unilateral involvement. Common comorbidities are glaucoma. High potency steroids are mostly used for the treatment of PSS. Mild or no visual impairment are seen in most of the Posner Schlossman syndrome patients.**Keywords:** Posner Schlossman syndrome, Clinical profile, Visual impairment

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Introduction

Posner-Schlossman syndrome (PSS) is a disease of non-granulomatous anterior uveitis with recurrent episodes, often accompanied by elevated intraocular pressure (IOP) [1]. Historically, PSS was regarded as a self-limiting disease with a favourable prognosis, leading to the neglect of long-term follow-up and management, particularly regarding IOP. However, as research into PSS has advanced and long-term patient follow-ups have been conducted, it has been discovered that secondary glaucoma may develop in some cases [2, 3].

Symptoms are usually minimal and include blurring of vision and haloes with pain described mostly as mild discomfort [4]. On examination, there may be no inflammation or mild inflammation in the anterior chamber with or without accompanying keratic precipitates (KPs)

on the corneal endothelium, corneal edema due to the high IOP, and open angles on gonioscopy, with most presenting with nonglaucomatous damage (in the initial stages). Iris atrophy may be seen in recurrent cases [5]. The KPs are usually very scanty and are inferior stellar KPs and have been called "sentinel KPs" [6]. Most often, patients give a history of recurrence of these symptoms.

PSS may resolve spontaneously within days to weeks after onset, but anti-glaucomatous and anti-inflammatory treatment is still indicated to control intraocular pressure (IOP) and inflammation for better prognosis. Some studies have shown an association of primary open-angle glaucoma and PSS [7,8] and glaucomatous damage from PSS itself has been noted [9,10].

In the recent two decades, PSS was found to be challenging to cure and also could cause

irreversible visual impairment in some patients [9]. Treatments were directed towards controlling the inflammation and related IOP elevation [11]. Even in some cases, surgical management like trabeculectomy was used to treat PSS to control the elevated IOP [12]. Moreover, the dynamic characteristics of pathophysiology in PSS are still not clear. Therefore, it is crucial to recognize the characteristics of PSS to reduce the risk of recurrence and visual damage. Objectives of our study was to evaluate the Clinical profile and management of Posner Schlossman syndrome in tertiary care center of North Bihar.

Material and Methods

The present study was conducted in the Department of Ophthalmology, Sri Krishna medical College & Hospital, India during a period from January 2024 to September 2024.

A total of 9002 new patients were visited to the OPD of the Department of Ophthalmology during the study period. The eye Smart EMR was screened for patients with a documented ocular diagnosis of PSS in one or both eyes. The diagnosis was made on the basis of the presence of mainly unilateral recurrent mild non-granulomatous iritis with cells in the anterior chamber, with/without fine KPs,

elevated IOP, open angles on gonioscopy, without posterior synechiae or posterior uveitis, with the attack lasting few days to weeks. Other causes of uveitis were ruled out by certain investigations: tuberculin skin test, chest X-ray, venereal disease research laboratory test (VDRL), fluorescent treponemal antibody absorption test (FTA-ABS), IgG for toxoplasmosis, and serum angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) test. Exclusion criteria were patients with normal IOP (<21 mmHg), patients with any other ocular disease (other than cataract), previous intraocular surgery, and glaucoma secondary to other causes such as steroid-induced glaucoma and post-traumatic glaucoma. A total of 30 patients were identified with PSS. A total of 36 eyes diagnosed with PSS and these patients were further analyzed for clinical information.

Results

In the present study, out 9004 eyes patients, 30 patients were diagnosed with PSS in at least one eye. Rate of prevalence was 0.003%. The mean age of the patients was 42.34 ± 11.23 years. The most common age group of the patients was 31–40 years (42%), followed by 21–30 years (32%), 41–50 years (18%) and 51–60 years (8%).

Figure 1: Age wise distribution of PSS patients

Figure 2: Gender wise distribution of PSS patients

In the present study, Males were 22(73.33%) and females were 8(26.67%).

Out of the 30 patients with PSS, 16(53.33%) were affected in the right eye and 9(30%) were affected

in the left eye. In 5(16.67%) patients, the affliction was bilateral in nature.

Figure 3: Laterality of eye involvement in PSS patients

Presenting visual acuity

Table 2: Visual acuity of patients with PSS

Visual acuity	No. of eye (N=36)	Percentage
Mild/No visual impairment (>20/70)	22	61.11%
Moderate (<20/70 to 20/200)	4	11.11%
Severe (<20/200 to 20/400)	1	2.78%
Blindness (>20/400 to 20/1200)	1	2.78%
Blindness (>20/1200 to PL).	2	5.55%
Blindness (NPL).	1	2.78%
Unspecified	5	5.55%

Out of the 36 eyes, 22(61.11%) eyes had mild or no visual impairment (visual acuity better than 20/70), 4(11.11%) eyes had moderate visual impairment (<20/70 to 20/200). 1(2.78%) eye had severe visual impairment (<20/200 to 20/400). 2(5.55%) eyes had blindness (>20/400 to 20/1200). 1(2.78%) eyes had blindness (>20/1200 to PL). 1(2.78%) eye had blindness (NPL). And the visual acuity was undetermined or unspecified in 5(13.89%) eyes. The mean logMAR at presentation was 0.43 ± 0.65.

Anterior segment, gonioscopy, and optic disc findings: KPs were found in 16(44.44%) eyes, anterior chamber cells in 13(36.11%) eyes, and iris atrophy in 3(8.33%) eyes.

Among the 36 eyes, a cup: disc ratio of 0.1–0.4 was documented in 13(36.11%) eyes, 0.5–0.7 in 8(22.22%) eyes, and > 0.7 in 6(16.67%) eyes. The gonioscopy findings showed an open angle in 32 (88.89%) eyes and a closed angle in 4 (11.11%) eyes.

Intraocular Pressure: Among the 36 eyes, IOP of 1–9 mmHg was documented in 1(33.33%) eye, 10–21 mmHg in 0 (0%) eyes, 22–30 mmHg in 5(13.88%) eyes, and >30 mmHg in 26(72.22%) eyes. The mean IOP was 32.76 ± 16.27 mmHg.

Table 1: Ocular comorbidities in PSS patient

Ocular comorbidities	No. of eyes (N=36)	Percentage
Cataract	3	8.33%
Glaucoma	10	27.78%

In the present study, among the 36 eyes, cataract was seen in 3(8.33%) eyes and glaucoma in 10(27.78%) eyes.

Medical Treatment: At presentation 22(73.33%) patients were on oral acetazolamide. 6(16.67%) eyes were on one topical AGM, 12(33.33%) were on two topical AGM, 9(25%) were on three topical

AGM, and 1(2.7%) eye were on four topical AGM.

High-potency steroids were prescribed to 20(55.56%) eyes and low-potency steroids to 16(44.44%) eyes. Oral antivirals prescribed included acyclovir in 8(26.67%) patients, valaciclovir in 2(6.67%) patients, and ganciclovir in 1(2.7%) patient. Steroids were prescribed in the

majority of cases for 1 or 2 months, with 13(36.11%) eyes for a duration of 1 month and 24(66.67%) eyes for a duration of 2 months. The rest were prescribed steroids for either a short duration or a longer duration.

2(5.56%) eyes were prescribed steroids for a short period of 2 weeks and 7(19.44%) eyes were prescribed steroids for 3 months and 1(2.78%) eye for 4 months. 23(63.89%) eyes were continued on AGMs till the last visit due to glaucomatous disc damage and target IOP not being achieved. The rest, however, required AGMs for a limited period during the attack, with 2(5.56%) requiring AGMs for 2 weeks, 19(52.78%) eyes for 1 month, 11(30.55%) eyes for 2 months, 5(13.89%) eyes for 3 months, and 1(2.7%) eye for 4 months.

7(19.44%) Eyes had one recurrent attack, 5(13.89%) eyes had two recurrent attacks, 3(8.33%) eyes had three attacks, 2(5.56%) had four attacks, 1(2.78%) eye (0.77%) had five attacks, 1(2.78%) eyes (3.08%) had six attacks, and 12(33.33%) eyes had no documented recurrent attacks till the time of follow-up.

Surgical Treatment

Among the 36 eyes, trabeculectomy was performed in 4 (6.92%) eyes and cataract surgery in 2 (3.85%) eyes. there were 3 male patients and 2 female patients who required trabeculectomy, with all patients requiring surgery due to uncontrolled IOP despite maximal medical therapy and/or disc and visual field changes. The average age at presentation was 40.35 ± 12.89 years, with the baseline IOP being 43.22 ± 4.12 mmHg.

Before trabeculectomy, 1(2.78%) eye was on low-potency steroids, 1(2.78%) was on high-potency steroids, 1(2.78%) was on topical NSAIDs, and 1(2.78%) was not using any topical steroids.

The average follow-up of the patients was 380 ± 564 days, with an average of 4 ± 8 visits. The IOP on the final visit was 13.42 ± 4.42 mmHg, with 2(5.56%) eyes were requiring adjunctive AGM to control IOP. 1(2.78%) eye had one recurrence, whereas the rest had not any recurrence post-surgery. There were no intraoperative or postoperative complications.

Discussions

Posner-Schlossman syndrome (PSS), also known as a glaucomatocyclitic crisis, is a well-known rare ocular disease [11]. PSS was first reported by Posner and Schlossman in 1948, and the initial report on PSS suggested that the attacks were unilateral and did not cause permanent damage to the eyes [13].

Rates of incidence of the disease vary from region to region. PSS makes up 1.7%[14] to 4.3%[19]

among all uveitis cases in Japan. In China, an annual incidence of 3.91 in 100,000 population has been reported.[15] In Finland, the incidence reported is 0.4 with a prevalence of 1.9/100000[16]. In our study, rate of prevalence was 0.003%.

In Europe, the common age group was 20–30 years of age,[21] whereas it was 30–50 years in Asia [17].

In the present study, most common age group of the patients was 31–40 years (42%), followed by 21–30 years (32%). Males seem to be more at risk [2,18] with the common age group being between the second and 3rd decade [16,17]. In the present study, PSS was more common in males (73.33%) than females (26.67%). An annual incidence of 4.33/100000 in men and 3.35/100000 in women has been reported in China [15]. The etiology of PSS remains still unknown. There have been numerous postulations for the pathogenesis of PSS including autonomic deregulation and infections. Herpes simplex or cytomegalovirus (CMV) has been suggested as etiologies for PSS due to their high express in the aqueous humor during acute attacks [19,20]. And some researchers considered that these results may have a potentially significant impact on the management of PSS [21].

In the present study, out of the 30 patients with PSS, 16(53.33%) were affected in the right eye and 9(30%) were affected in the left eye. In 5(16.67%) patients, the affliction was bilateral in nature.

Management strategies are concentrated on controlling the acute rise of IOP, controlling inflammation/uveitis (trabeculitis), and prevention of recurrence and complications such as long-term chronic glaucoma. Evidence, however, does exist that spontaneous resolution does occur, even without treatment [22]. Topical steroids cause reduction of the uveitis/trabeculitis, but they are unlikely to reduce the rate of recurrence [23]. Topical steroids range from high-potency steroids such as prednisolone/dexamethasone to low-potency ones such as fluorometholone/loteprednol, with inflammation being controlled in either [24]. High-potency steroids were prescribed in a higher number of patients in our study. Topical beta-blockers, carbonic anhydrase inhibitors (CAIs), and/or alpha agonists, or a combination of these, are used to curb the rise in IOP, with most cases requiring oral CAIs. Slow tapering or cessation can be done over a period of time with the resolution of the attack. Prostaglandin analogs and pilocarpine are usually avoided as they may aggravate the inflammation [25]. Oral valganciclovir, although favourable in terms of success rate, has a high recurrence rate, most probably due to its virostatic property [26]. And its use would warrant monitoring of white

blood cell count.[9] Acyclovir was most commonly prescribed in our patients. Intravitreal valganciclovir has been tried,[27] but is debatable as most of these cases would present with only anterior uveitis with no features of posterior uveitis. Glaucoma filtration surgeries augmented with anti-metabolites or glaucoma drainage devices are reserved for recalcitrant high IOP cases or for cases with chronic glaucoma with glaucomatous optic neuropathy [18,28,29,30]. Different studies have reported different rates of glaucoma filtration surgeries.

PSS patients with glaucomatous damage are more likely to have iris depigmentation. Kam et al. [2] identified iris depigmentation as a clinical biomarker for predicting chronic or recurrent anterior uveitis CMV infection in a prospective cohort study [31].

In the present study, trabeculectomy was performed in 6.92% of eyes. A study from South Korea showed rates of 6.1% for trabeculectomy and 15.3% for glaucoma drainage device (GDD) [2]. The same study found that patients who required surgery were those with a higher IOP, increased frequency of attacks, higher number of topical anti-glaucoma medications, more iris changes, decreased corneal endothelial cell density, thinner RNFL, and worse mean deviation (MD) on visual fields [2].

Our study reports less occurrence of recurrences post trabeculectomy. The occurrence of glaucoma was as high as 10(27.78%) eyes in our study. It has been hypothesized that mild inflammation does keep recurring, which goes undetected, leading to optic nerve damage and retinal nerve fiber layer (RNFL) thinning [32]. Therefore, it can be rationalized that continuation of glaucoma medications is important in patients who show glaucomatous optic nerve damage, those with a large cup: disc ratio, or focal thinning of neuroretinal rim, [1,30] with some even advocating to continue medications in those at risk of NAION, as cases of NAION post PSS have been reported [29].

Previous study also implied that PSS might be related to vascular endothelial dysfunction [34], inflammatory cytokines [35], allergy [36], genetic susceptibility [37,38], and viral infection [39]. Many previous studies have reported cytomegalovirus in the aqueous humor or serum [40] and ganciclovir eye drop effective for PSS patients [41].

A few cases of bilateral PSS have been reported [42,43] with some being described to have the attack at the same time bilaterally and others one after the other alternately. We noted 6(3.17%) patients with this bilateral affliction. A better understanding of the pathomechanisms and risk

factors of PSS is essential to prevent the onset of glaucoma, a preventable but irreversible case of loss of vision.

Jap *et al.* in their retrospective review of 50 patients (53 eyes) with PSS, found glaucoma in 14 eyes (26.4%) as a result of repeated PSS attacks [9].

Darchuk *et al.* reported a PSS case with optic disc damage and visual field loss [44]. Kim *et al.* also described a pale optic disc and a superior paracentral visual field defect in a 32-year-old man of PSS at his fifth attack [10].

Conclusions

The present study concluded that the PSS is more common in young to middle aged population. It is predominantly unilateral involvement. Common comorbidities are glaucoma. High potency steroids are mostly used for the treatment of PSS. Mild or no visual impairment are seen in most of the Posner Schlossman syndrome patients.

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